

A Cross Sectional Survey on Assessing the Psychological & Financial Happiness Among Software Professionals in Telangana State

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Abstract:- Happiness is a state of inner comfort that a person encounter when fine things occur in a particular time. Most of the people are busy in orientation of their goals for a good financial status in cost of their happiness. As there is a tight schedule for the IT professionals, we would like to know whether those people are happy with their financial status and psychological status. Due to this scenario this study was conducted to find the psychological & financial happiness among software professionals in Telangana state.

Using a purposive sampling method an online survey using self administered questionnaire was sent to employees in the software profession in Telangana state. They were asked to fill the questionnaire via Google forms. The statistical score for the responses were calculated and analysis was performed.

In this study overall 79% of the study participants are psychologically happy where as 67% of the study participants are financially not happy. The common human nature is how much ever we earn we doesn't get satisfied. The other reason may be software professionals are working more than they get paid.

Keywords:- Happiness, smile, software professionals, hormones.

I. INTRODUCTION

Happiness is defined as an excited state of a living body that has been regulated in both body and mind as an outcome to a satisfactory situation in life or by experiencing a pleasurable moment in life. People live for happiness and people addicted to happiness¹. Happiness often co-exists with a specific facial expression called the smile². Other ways for the expression of happiness is entertainment, love,

inquisitiveness and triumph. These helps for the normal development and comfortable life³. The phrase “quality of life”, well-being and happiness indicate different meanings. Sometimes they are used as an umbrella term for all value and at other times to indicate special means. It presents a classification based on 2 bi-partitions between life chances, life results and between outer and inner qualities. Together the dichotomies imply four qualities of life. They are Livability of environment, Utility of life, Life ability of person, Appreciation of life or subjective enjoyment of life.⁴

The word life satisfaction is mostly used for overall happiness. Even when there is center of attention on subjective satisfaction with life there are still different explanations associated with the word happiness. The acquaintance of enjoyment can be impermanent or enduring. Again the phrase happiness is used for both situations, on occasions it refers to passing moods and on other occasions to stable satisfaction. There are four kinds of satisfaction: Instant satisfaction, Domain satisfaction, Top experience, lasting satisfaction with one's life as a whole.

When assessing the praising of life we tend to use two more or less distinct sources of documentation: our effects and their thoughts⁵. The important correlates of happiness are social in nature. In contrast to the modest demographic correlates of happiness and well-being, the robust correlates of happiness are Number of peer group, marital status, Being socially confident person, being devoted, Pursuing activities in leisure time, Employment (not income), Gratitude⁶. Subjective well-being is the systematic term for happiness and life satisfaction thought and feeling that your life is going well. People's level of Subjective well-being is influenced by both Internal factors (such as personality and outlook) and External factors (society in which they live). The major determinants of Subjective well-being are person's inborn

temperament, quality of their social relationships, the sources they live in, their ability to meet their basic needs.

Outcomes of subjective well-being have found that happy people are more likely to be healthier and live longer to have better social relationships and to be more constructive at work. In other words, people elevated in subjective well-being seen to be healthier and function more beneficially compared to people when are chronically emphasized, melancholy or irritated. Thus happiness does not just feel good but it is good for people and for those around them.⁷

There are 3 major types of happiness they are High life satisfaction, frequent positive feelings, Low negative feelings there are some hormones produced in our body which makes us happy⁸ Hormones are chemical messengers synthesized by endocrine glands. They doesn't act directly on target cells they combined with receptor present on target cells and form hormone receptor complex⁹. Happy hormones include Dopamine, Serotonin, Oxytocin and Endorphin.

Even while we are in stress ,we can stimulate our happy hormones by adding some food substances like chocolates,probiotics,green leafy vegetables,proteins etc.Some life style alterations such as daily morning exercise, meditation,exposure to morning sunlight,Enjoying music,and refreshed sleep will also increases your happy hormones. Targeting an aim and attaining the target will increase dopamine, which acts as a chemical messenger communicating messages between neurons in your brain and rest of the body, if there is correct balance of dopamine you will be happy and be motivated¹⁰. Revealing our gratitude will increase serotonin which also plays a major role in regulating your mood. Playing with pets and spending time with our loved ones will increase oxytocin, doing morning exercise daily for at least 20 minutes will boost endorphins and thus making you happy. Spending time with loved ones and sharing problems can also reduces stress. So those who are in great worry and those who are really struggling because of stress can include these life style modifications to reduce their pressure level and become happy.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this cross sectional prevalence study using non randomized purposive sampling method by an online survey using self descriptive questionnaire via Google form was sent to software professionals working in various companies in Telangana State. This study was done on June 2022.Consent is taken from all the participants who had participated in this study. Their scoring was then calculated, assessed and analyzed by the feedback obtained from the questioner to evaluate the grading of financial and psychological happiness.

Questionnaire on assessing psychological and financial happiness among software professionals.

1. We are conducting a study on assessing psychological and financial happiness among software professionals. . Do you agree to submit this form and help us in our survey?
 - Yes
 - No

2. Your Name?
3. Your Age?
4. Your Gender?
5. Name of company you are working at?
6. Current relationship status
 - Single
 - Married
7. What is current employment status?
 - Permanent full time
 - Non permanent full time
 - Permanent part time
 - Non permanent part time

On scale of 1 to 7 how much you give to yourself

1. In general I consider myself happy
2. Compare to most of my peers, I consider myself happy
3. How much do you feel satisfied with your life?
4. How much you maintain the relationship with your family members?
5. How often do you feel lonely?
 - always
 - very often
 - sometimes
 - rarely
 - never
6. How often do you feel depressed?
 - Always
 - Very often
 - sometimes
 - rarely
 - never
7. How often you procrastinate about the status of your personal goals in life?
 - Always
 - Very often
 - sometimes
 - rarely
 - never
8. How often do you feel happy?
 - Always
 - Very often
 - sometimes
 - rarely
 - never
9. How often do you feel positive?
 - Always
 - Very often
 - sometimes
 - rarely
 - never
10. How often do you feel angry?
 - Always
 - Very often
 - sometimes
 - rarely
 - never

- 11. Do you feel financially satisfied in your life?
 - Yes
 - No
- 12. Are you satisfied with your pay scale (salary)?
 - Yes
 - No
- 13. Are you happy with your professional life?
 - Yes
 - No
- 14. Are you happy with the relationships in your life?
 - Yes
 - No
- 15. Do you feel responsible in doing work?
 - Yes
 - No
- 16. Are you having a refreshed sleep?
 - Yes
 - No
- 17. Do you content with the current status of life?
 - Yes
 - No

- 18. Do you have any other concerns that you would like to mention?
 - If yes -----

III. RESULTS

The study was done in online mode (Google form). Software professionals working in various companies in Telangana state who was willing to participate were included in this study. This study was done on June 2022, 104 software professionals participated in this study, where in 82 participants are psychologically happy 22 participants are unhappy. Financially 34 participants are happy and 70 participants are unhappy.

Total Study Participants	No of participants -Psychologically happy	No of participants - Psychologically Unhappy
104	82	22

Table 1:- Number of Participants Psychologically happy and unhappy

Fig 1:- Number of Participants Psychologically happy and unhappy

Total Study Participants	No of participants -Financially happy	No of participants -Financially Unhappy
104	34	70

Table 2:- Number of Participants Financially happy and unhappy

Fig 2:- Number of Participants financially happy and unhappy

IV. DISCUSSION

In day to day life man is in greed of money and in search of aspiring the heights of carrier. In this scenario we had done this study to assess financial and psychological happiness of software. In this study we have observed that among 104 study participants of which 62(60%) are male and 42(40%) are female, 21(20%) are married and 83(80%) are unmarried. Among them 82(79%) of the study participants are psychologically happy and 22(21%) study participants are psychologically not happy.

Among 83 unmaried employees 76(92%) are happy and remaining 7(8%) are not happy psychologically. Among 21 married employees 6(29%) are happy and remaining 15(71%) are unhappy. On considering gender among 62 male employees, 57(92%) males are psychologically happy, 5(8%) males are psychologically not happy, among 42 females, 25(60%) females are psychologically happy and 17(40%) female employees are not happy.

So by this study we found that unmarried employees are psychologically more happy than married employees and male employees are more happy psychologically than female employees.

While assessing financial happiness among 104 participants 34(33%) participants are happy and remaining 70(67%) of study participants are not happy. Among 21 married employees only 3(14%) are happy financially remaining 18(86%) are unhappy financially. Among 83 unmarried employees 31(37%) employees are happy

financially, 52(63%) employees are not happy, so that both married and unmarried employees are unhappy financially but married employees are more unhappy.

Considering gender for assessing financial happiness among 62 males, 33(53%) is unhappy financially, 29(47%) male employees are only happy. Among 42 females 41(98%) females are happy financially only one (2%) employee is unhappy. So that male employees are more unhappy financially than female employees.

V. CONCLUSION

By this cross sectional study we want to conclude two things that Software employees here at Hyderabad are Psychologically Happy and financially Unhappy with their pay to the work. Considering Psychological happiness, we can see the participants (software employees) are happy with their work, work place and having good relationship with their colleagues. Even though financially being unhappy or not satisfied but most of the employees are responsible to their work and they are maintaining the happy and healthy relationship with their family members, friends and colleagues. Irrespective of their financial dissatisfaction we observe the participants are more workaholic, positive feeling towards their life & goals besides the negativity. We can say that psychological happiness is much important for human being for healthy life; here in the survey the participants are happy which helps in adding healthy society together.

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